

THE CONCEPT OF THEFT OF OTHERS PROPERTY USING INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AND ITS ESSENCE

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ANNOTATION. This paper discusses new information technologies, their use for property theft, and explores different scholarly approaches as well as their application in legislation and standards, both national and international.

KEY WORDS: information technology, theft, international standards, database, telecommunications, collection, creation, storage, collection, processing, release of information, processes, methods.

Today the number of Internet users in our country has increased to 31 million. The number of mobile Internet users is 29.5 million. The level of mobile communications coverage in the republic has reached 99%, and broadband mobile Internet coverage has reached 98%[1]. In turn, these opportunities require each country to focus on timely prevention of cyber threats that may arise in the process of globalization of digital technologies.

Indeed, in accordance with the rapid development of information and communication technologies in the world, the effective use of their capabilities by various criminal elements poses a threat to the processes of safe use of cyberspace.

It should be noted that most threats in cyberspace are aimed at causing material damage to the state, society and citizens[2]. The size of this damage increases every year in proportion to the number of threats.

According to data, the amount of damage caused to the global economy by cyber attacks has quadrupled over the past four years, and by 2022 this figure will exceed \$8 trillion. In turn, experts predict that these threats will cause damage to the global economy amounting to 11 trillion US dollars by the end of 2025 and 90 trillion US dollars by 2030 [3].

This indicates that criminals who carry out cyber threats effectively use the capabilities of information technology when committing crimes related to the theft of other people's property.

To organize activities aimed at the early detection of these acts and improve the fight against them, it is necessary first of all to understand the

meaning of the concept of theft of other's property using information technology.

There are similarities and inconsistencies in the definitions given in international and national legal norms of the term and content of the concept of information technology. The words mentioned in them are "information and communication technologies", and in others "computer technology" have a similar meaning to the word information technology.

In international and regional documents we can observe that the concept of information technology is defined in a unique way.

In particular, information technologies are described as information and communication technologies in the draft UN Convention on Combating the Use of Information and Communication Technologies for Criminal Purposes[4], which includes processes and methods for creating, processing and disseminating information, as well as methods and the means of their implementation.

The Budapest Convention on Computer Crime of November 23, 2003 defines a computer system as any device or group of interconnected or linked devices, operating in accordance with one or more programs, performing automated data processing[5].

According to the agreement "On cooperation of member states of the Commonwealth of Independent States in the fight against crimes in the field of information technology" [6] (September 28, 2018, Dushanbe), information technology is the collection, creation, storage of collection, processing, issuance, copying information, which is a set of methods, production processes and software and hardware, combined into a technological complex that ensures transmission, distribution and protection.

In the "Annotated Dictionary of Information and Communication Technologies" [7], published with the support of the United Nations Development Program, the concept of information technology is defined in a broad sense and in a narrow sense.

According to the dictionary, examples of information technology in the broad sense include the use of an office abacus and the printing of books. It is noted that the term information technology in a narrow sense is associated with the use of modern electronic equipment in order to reduce the labor intensity of processes that use this technology to process information, and increase their reliability and speed.

Moreover, information technology in this dictionary is described as the

ways, means and methods of using computer technology in the process of collecting, processing, storing, transmitting and using data.

Scholars I. Yu. Kulikova, N. V. Muravyova, V. A. Borovykh in their manuals [8] understand information technology as search, reception, transmission, collection, processing, collection, storage, distribution and (or) a set of process of representation, their methods, and use and protection of information. It is noted that all information technologies used in professional activities specialize in providing various types of information for drawing conclusions and taking any actions in the future.

International and national standards also approach the concept of information technology in a unique way.

According to the international standard “Systems and Software Engineering – Dictionary” (ISO/IEC/IEEE 24765:2017), information technology refers to the resources necessary to obtain, process, store and distribute information[9].

According to the requirements specified in paragraph 2.2.6 of the State Standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan (UzDST 1047:2018[10]), information technology is: 1) a system of models, methods and means of implementing information processes; 2) a system of methods for collecting, storing, searching, processing, and providing information; 3) a set of methods, devices and processes used for collecting, storing, processing and distributing information.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Informatization” refers to information technologies as a set of methods, devices, methods and processes used to collect, store, search, process and disseminate information[11].

Based on the definitions given to the concept of information technology by international and regional organizations, standards, legislation of foreign countries, and independent experts, we can conclude that the current definition of the concept of information technology does not fully cover its scope.

In particular, according to the current definition, the concept of information technology does not cover the processes of creating, processing, issuing, copying, transferring and protecting information, and it is also not clearly stated that it includes software.

In our opinion, information technologies can be defined as methods, software and hardware tools and processes combined into a technological complex that provides collection, storage, search, processing, output, copying, transmission, processing and its distribution, protection. corresponding.

At this stage, we will consider what the sign of the use of information

technology covers in cases of theft of other's property.

According to the Merriam-Webster dictionary, the word “use” means “to put into action or service”, “avail oneself of”. To use, therefore, means to “avail oneself of opportunities for one’s needs and desires”[12].

Based on this definition, the use of information technology is a sign of the objective side of individual crimes, as well as a factor in the emergence of a number of new crimes or the formation of new forms of existing criminal acts.

This indicates a tendency to commit new crimes related to the theft of other people’s property using information technology[13]. In fact, these crimes have the characteristics of cybercrime[14], and the expansion of the areas of application of information technologies remains one of the factors in the growth of crimes committed using these technologies[15].

Therefore, in our opinion, when expressing the sign of the use of information technology, it is necessary to take into account the use of technical devices, software, electronic access tools, malware and other devices in order to facilitate methods of committing a crime.

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